

Metal Reagents in Organic Reactions. Part-VI^{1,2}. Oxidation of Indoles with Thallium(III) Acetate[†]

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The action of thallium(III) acetate on a number of indoles, differently substituted in the 2- and 3-positions, has been investigated. Monomeric and 'dimeric' oxidation products are obtained; the structures of the products depend on the substituents present in the substrate. A novel oxidative dimerisation of 2,3-disubstituted indoles to indolo[3,2-*b*]carbazoles is observed. The generation of the products could be rationalised by the initial formation of an unstable, non-isolable 3-thallated-indolenine derivative.

A large number of publications have appeared on the reactions of thallium(III) salts with different classes of compounds, including benzenoid aromatics, olefins, acetylenes and glycols³⁻⁷. Less work has been done on the reactions of heterocycles with thallium(III) species (for example, Ref. 1). We report here the action of thallium(III) acetate (TTA) on indole and its derivatives, viz. indole, 2-methyl-, 2-phenyl-, 3-methyl-, 2,3-dimethyl- and 2-ethyl-3-methylindole. Most of the reactions were carried out in acetic acid containing a small amount (5-10%) of water. A preliminary account of some of this work had appeared earlier².

Results and Discussion

Reactions of indole and its derivatives with TTA gave both monomeric and 'dimeric' oxidation products which were isolated and characterised. The nature of the products depend on the substituents present at the 2- and/or 3-positions. The course of these reactions could be rationalised by postulating an initial electrophilic attack of TTA on the C₃-position of the indole as the first step to give 3-thallated-indolenine derivatives (1) as intermediates (Eqn. 1).

These underwent further transformations *in situ* to the products. It has not been possible to isolate any of the postulated organothallium intermediates on account of their instability.

A list of the products obtained is given in Table 1. The structure and stereochemistry of the products were assigned on the basis of spectroscopic and chemical analyses. In all cases large amounts of highly coloured polar compounds were formed—these could not be isolated and characterised.

Indole: 3-Acetoxyindole^{8a} was obtained as the sole product. Nucleophilic displacement of thallium by acetate in the intermediate 3-thallated-indolenine occurs with concomitant

reduction of thallium from the +3 to +1 oxidation state. This reaction thus provides a suitable method for the introduction of an oxygenated function at the 3-position of indole.

TABLE 1—REACTION PRODUCTS OF INDOLE DERIVATIVES WITH TTA*

Substrate	Reaction conditions		Product	Yield
	Temp. °C	Time h		
Indole	30	2	3-Acetoxyindole (1)	43
Skatole (3-Methylindole)	25-30	70	3-Acetoxy-3-methyl-oxindole (3)	28
			3-Methyloxindole (2)	8
			Dimer (4)	10
2-Methylindole	25-30	20	5	8
2-Phenylindole	(a) 25-30 then 45-50 (b) 45	70 24 100	6 6	32 16
2,3-Dimethylindole (7)	(a) 25-30 (b) 25-30 (MeOH)	24 24	9 11 9	40 5 8
2-Ethyl-3-methylindole (8)	25-30	30	10 12	34 22
1,2,3-Tri-methylindole	(a) 25-30 (b) 50	4 days 4 days	No reaction No reaction	- -

*Reaction medium: 90-95% acetic acid, unless otherwise mentioned.

3-Methylindole (skatole): A complex mixture of products resulted on TTA oxidation. The three major components were isolated and characterised as 3-methyloxindole (2), 3-acetoxy-3-methyl oxindole (3) and 3-methyl-2-(3'-methyloxindole-3')indole (4). The probable mechanistic pathways to these products are rationalised in Scheme 1. 3-Methyloxindole has been also reported to be produced by the oxidation of 3-methylindole by peracetic acid and potassium persulphate^{9,10}. In the present case it was probably formed by hydroxylation at C₂ of the indolenine system followed by loss of ROH (R = H, COCH₃). Hydroxylation at C₂ of the indolenine system followed by oxidation by TTA would lead to product 3. 3-Methyloxindole (2) under the reaction conditions afforded 3, which could therefore arise

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.
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Scheme 1

by an alternative route. Product 4 was obtained from a nucleophilic attack by a second skatole molecule on the intermediate 3-thallated-indolenine derivative.

3-Acetoxy-3-methyloxindole (3) showed the typical oxindole uv (λ_{\max} (EtOH) 248, 283 nm; $\log \epsilon$ 3.95, 3.23) and ^1H nmr signals for the 3-methyl and 3-acetoxymethyl groups (δ 1.55, 3H, s and 1.99, 3H, s). The presence of the oxindole moiety in 4 was revealed by uv maxima at 216, 231, 252 and 286 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.25, 4.09, 4.00 and 2.53), an ir band at 1685 cm^{-1} (characteristic of the amide carbonyl) and a signal at δ 8.66 (NH) in its ^1H nmr spectrum, 4 showed two tertiary methyls at δ 1.55 and 1.99 in its ^1H nmr spectrum.

2-Methylindole : The product 2-methyl-3-(2'-methylindo-xyl-2')indole (5) was probably formed (Scheme 2) through the intermediacy of an indoxyl derivative. Oxidation to the indolenine followed by nucleophilic attack at C₂

by a second 2-methylindole molecule furnished the product 5. Compound 5 has also been reported to be formed by the action of peracetic acid on 2-methylindole¹¹; this experiment was repeated by us, when 5 was obtained.

2-Phenylindole : 2-Phenylindole similarly afforded a product, 2-phenyl-3-(2'-phenylindoxyl-2')indole (6). We found that unlike 2-methylindole, 2-phenylindole did not furnish 6 on peracetic acid oxidation.

2,3-Dimethylindole and 2-ethyl-3-methylindole : The 2,3-dialkyl indoles (7,8) were found to give the most interesting results. These underwent a novel oxidative dimerisation to yield 6,6a,12,12a-tetrahydroindolo[3,2-b]carbazoles (9,10) as the major products in acetic acid medium with TTA. The same products were also formed in methanolic media although in much lower yield. Our preliminary communication constituted the first report in which these particular indolocarbazoles had been synthesised². The

Scheme 2

present oxidative dimerisation method is convenient for preparation of the indolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole skeleton. Initial 3-thallation produced an indolenine derivative; oxidative dimerisation then occurred via the tautomeric enamine form to give the products (Scheme 3). For compounds 7 and 8, the products of oxidation of the 2-alkyl group, viz. 2-aldehydro-3-methylindole (11) and 2-acetyl-3-methylindole (12) respectively, were also obtained. Products arising from oxidation of the 2-alkyl group by lead tetra-acetate (LTA) had been reported earlier. We performed LTA-oxidations of 7 and 8 under conditions similar to those employed for the TTA-oxidations. The sole products were 11 and 12 respectively — the indolocarbazoles 9 and 10 could not be detected even on TLC analysis. It is apparent therefore that the reactivity of the initially formed 3-metallated-indolenines are different for the thallium(III) and lead(IV) species.

The tetrahydroindolocarbazoles (9,10) exhibited typical indolenine uv maxima (223–225 and 260–263 nm; log ϵ 4.45–4.78 and 4.02–4.46) and ir absorptions (1602–1607, 1565–1575, 768–770 and 750–752 cm^{-1}). The structure and stereochemistry of the compounds were settled from nmr studies. The ^1H - and ^{13}C nmr showed the presence of only half the number of signals expected, indicating the symmetrical nature of the compounds. The marked difference in chemical shifts of the two pairs of methylene protons of 9 indicated the *trans*-structure (9a) rather than the *cis*- (9b). The equatorial protons at C_6 and C_{12} are nearly co-planar

with the adjacent $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ - group in 9a and are strongly deshielded. The axial protons, however, appear at the normal value as there is practically no deshielding (or shielding) effect. In 9b, the central ring would be forced to take up a twist-boat conformation, where the dihedral angle between the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ - bond and the two methylene protons are nearly the same so that a marked differentiation of these in the ^1H nmr would not be expected. Preliminary X-ray analysis indicated a centrosymmetric structure for product 9, in accordance with the *trans*-formulation (9a). The appearance of the C_6 -, C_{12} -protons in 10 in the normal region indicated their axial orientation in their ^1H nmr. Thus the methyls at these carbons are equatorial — their low chemical shift (δ 1.98) attesting to the fact that they lie in the deshielding region of the adjacent $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ - bonds.

The 6,6a,12,12a-tetrahydroindolocarbazole derivatives (9,10) on reduction with sodium borohydride afforded the 5,5a,6,6a,11,11a,12,12a-octahydroindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole derivatives 13 and 14. The presence of the indoline moiety in the latter was indicated by their uv absorption maxima (245–248 and 295–300 nm; log ϵ 3.58–4.22, 3.05–3.84). The ^1H nmr spectra of the compounds showed the symmetrical dimeric nature of the compounds. The magnitude of the coupling constants of the $\text{C}_{5a/11a}$ -protons (J 6.5 and 5 Hz for 13, and J 3.5 Hz for 14) indicated that these were equatorially disposed.

1,2,3-Trimethylindole failed to react even after several days. This seems to confirm that the absence of any substitution at the 1-position is necessary for reaction to occur. This is explicable as the intermediate 3-thallated-indolenine cannot be formed for a 1-substituted indole. 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydrocarbazole gave an intractable mixture of products.

Scheme 3

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (ethanol) were recorded on Carl-Zeiss VSU-1 and Varian 634S spectrophotometers, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra on Varian CFT-20, Varian XL-100 and Bruker-AM300L spectrometers, and mass spectra (70 eV) on a Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi RMU-6 instrument. Silica gel and silica gel G were used for column and thin-layer chromatography respectively. Analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 *in vacuo* at room temperature. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for dry-

ing organic solvents.

Indole and 3-methylindole (A.R., Merck) were used. 2-Methyl-^{8b}, 2-phenyl-¹² and 2-ethyl-3-methyl-¹³ indoles were obtained by literature methods from the appropriate phenylhydrazones by the Fischer synthesis using anhydrous zinc chloride as catalyst. 2,3-Dimethylindole was prepared from diethyl ketone phenylhydrazone by the PPA method of Fischer synthesis¹⁴. 1,2,3-Trimethylindole was obtained by *N*-methylation of the former¹⁵. TTA was prepared from thallium oxide⁶ and the Tl^{III} content determined by iodometric titration.

General method for reactions of indoles with thallium triacetate (TTA) in acetic acid : An approximately 10% solution of TTA (equimolar unless otherwise stated) in acetic acid containing 5–10% water was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the indole derivative dissolved in the same solvent at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The temperature was raised after the addition of TTA for some of the reactions. Details of reaction conditions are given in Table 1. The reactions were monitored by TLC. The reaction mixtures were worked up by neutralising the acetic acid with NaHCO_3 at 0° , and then extracting with methylene chloride. The methylene chloride extract was dried and concentrated to give a reddish or brownish gummy mass, which was chromatographed over silica-gel to isolate the products. Blank reactions were run in each case.

3-Acetoxyindole : Indole (468 mg, 4 mmol) in acetic acid (3 ml) and TTA (1.52 g, 4 mmol) in acetic acid (20 ml) after 2 h at 30° gave 3-acetoxyindole (300 mg, 43%), m.p. 128° (ether-petrol, 1 : 3) from petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluates (lit.^{8a} 127.5°) (Found : C, 68.5; H, 5.3; N, 8.1. M^+ 175. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 68.6; H, 5.2; N, 8.0%); ν_{max} 3340 (NH), 1740, 1240 and 1210 cm^{-1} (acetoxy); λ_{max} (EtOH) 240, 265, 280, 290 nm (log ϵ 3.70, 3.82, 3.84, 3.73); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 6.95–7.55 (6H, m, ArH and NH), 2.28 (3H, m, COCH_3). Unreacted indole (184 mg, 18%) was recovered from petrol-benzene (9 : 1) eluates.

Reaction with 3-methylindole (skatole) : 3-Methylindole (262 mg, 2 mmol) in acetic acid (7 ml) and TTA (765 mg, 2 mmol) in acetic acid (7 ml) after 70 h at room temperature gave 3-methyloxindole (2; 24 mg, 8%), 3-acetoxy-3-methyloxindole (3; 115 mg, 28%) and 4 (28 mg, 10%).

3-Acetoxy-3-methyloxindole (3) : M.p. 185° (benzene) (Found : C, 64.3; H, 5.5; N, 6.8. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$ requires : C 64.4; H, 5.4; N, 6.8%); ν_{max} 3200 (NH), 1732 (acetoxy), 1687 cm^{-1} (amide); λ_{max} 248, 283 nm (log ϵ 3.95, 3.23); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.38 (1H, s, disappeared on deuteration, NH), 6.6–7.3 (4H, m, ArH), 1.99 (3H, s, OCOMe), 1.55 (3H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-Me}$); m/z 205 (M^+ , 50%), 162 (M-Ac, 63), 146 (M-OAc, 53), 145 (M-HOAc, 30), 135 (M-CO- CH_2CO , 25), 117 (M-HOAc-CO), 43 (CH_3CO , 100).

3-Methyloxindole (2) : M.p. 117° (petrol-benzene, 1 : 1), lit.^{9,10} 121° ; identity established by comparison with authentic sample.

3-Methyl-2-(3'-methyloxindole-3')indole (4) : Yellow granules, m.p. $224\text{--}225^\circ$ (Found : C, 78.0; H, 5.9; N, 10.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 78.2; H, 5.8; N, 10.2%); ν_{max} 1685 cm^{-1} (lactam); λ_{max} (EtOH) 216, 231, 252, 286 nm (log ϵ 4.25, 4.09, 4.00, 2.53); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.66 (1H, s,

NH), 6.55–7.45 (8H, m, ArH), 1.99 (3H, s, Me), 1.56 (3H, s, Me); m/z 276 (M^+), 261 (M- CH_3), 233 (M- $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO}$), 218 (M-2 $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO}$), 247 (M-CHO), 138, 131 (3-methylindole), 117 (3-methyloxindole-CO), 109, 102, 89, 77, 63, 51.

Reaction of 2-methylindole : 2-Methylindole (1.048 g, 8 mmol) in acetic acid (8 ml) and TTA (3.04 g, 8 mmol) in acetic acid (35 ml) after 20 h at room temperature gave 2-methyl-3-(2'-methyloxindolyl-2')indole (5; 90 mg, 8%), m.p. 210° (benzene) (lit.¹¹ 212°), and another product (210 mg), m.p. 195° (dec.) (benzene-petrol) from benzene eluates.

2-Methyl-3-(2'-methyloxindolyl-2')indole (5) : (Found : C, 78.1; H, 6.0; N, 10.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 78.2; H, 5.8; N, 10.1%); ν_{max} 3440, 3260 (NH), 1675 cm^{-1} (lactam); λ_{max} (EtOH) 225, 260, 281, 288, 405 nm (log ϵ 4.63, 4.04, 3.91, 3.86, 3.53); λ_{max} (30% $\text{HClO}_4\text{-EtOH}$) 225, 256, 285, 334, 528 nm (log ϵ 4.44, 4.21, 3.97, 3.70, 3.60); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 6.6–7.8 (10H, m, ArH and NH), 2.35 (3H, s, $\text{C}_2\text{-Me}$), 1.84 (3H, s, $\text{C}_2\text{-Me}$); m/z 276 (M^+ , 58%), 261 (M-Me, 68), 248 (M-CO, 31), 233 (M-Me-CO, 63), 130 (46), 78 (100). Attempted sodium borohydride reduction of 5 in methanol failed.

Peracetic acid oxidation of 2-methylindole : 2-methylindole was converted to 5 with peracetic acid according to the method of Witkop¹¹. Direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., superimposable ir, ^1H nmr) showed the identity of this compound with the TTA product.

Reaction of 2-phenylindole : TTA (400 mg, 1.05 mmol) and 2-phenylindole (200 mg, 1.05 mmol) at room temperature (70 h) then at $45\text{--}50^\circ$ (24 h) gave 6 (64 mg, 32%), as yellow granules, m.p. 145° (cyclohexane). The compound was extracted from the reaction mixture with CH_2Cl_2 and purified by PTLC over silica gel G using benzene as the developing solvent (Found : C, 83.5; H, 5.1; N, 6.9. M^+ 400. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 84.0; H, 5.50; N, 7.0%); ν_{max} 3340–3440 (NH), 1685 cm^{-1} (amide carbonyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 224, 294, 409 nm (log ϵ 4.60, 4.10, 3.26); λ_{max} (30% $\text{HClO}_4\text{-EtOH}$) 222, 260, 302 (log ϵ 4.60, 4.10, 3.26); λ_{max} (30% $\text{HClO}_4\text{-EtOH}$) 222, 260, 302 (log ϵ 4.50, 4.05, 4.55); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 6.40–7.45 (complex m, ArH); m/z 400 (M^+ , 41%), 372 (M-CO, 39), 371 (M-CO-H, 100), 323 (M-Ph, 24), 295 (M-CO-Ph, 59), 208 (2-phenyl-3-indoxylyl, 5), 200 (M^{++} , 12), 180 (208-CO, 5). Unreacted 2-phenylindole (60 mg, 30%) was recovered. With a larger proportion of TTA (0.96 g, 2 mmol), 2-phenylindole (386 mg, 2 mmol) with a longer reaction time (100 h at 45°), the product 6 (65 mg, 16%) and unreacted 2-phenylindole (40 mg, 11%) were obtained. The lower yields indicated that 6

further reacted with excess TTA on prolonged treatment. 2-Phenylindole did not furnish **6** in a blank experiment without TTA, or on peracetic acid oxidation according to Wiberg's method¹¹.

Reaction of 2,3-dimethylindole (7) : TTA (2.67 g, 7 mmol) in acetic acid (30 ml) and 2,3-dimethylindole (1.02 g, 7 mmol) in acetic acid (15 ml) yielded **9** (400 mg, 40%), m.p. 282° (ethyl acetate) from the benzene-ethyl acetate eluates : (Found : C, 83.6; H, 6.3; N, 9.6. C₂₀H₁₈N₂ requires : C, 83.9; H, 6.3; N, 9.8%); ν_{\max} 1607, 1575, 852, 770, 752 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 223, 263 nm (log ϵ 4.46, 4.05); λ_{\max} (70% HClO₄) 241, 314 nm (log ϵ 3.95, 4.05); δ_{H} (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 7.22–7.78 (8H, m, ArH), 3.26 and 2.65 (2H, d, *J* 13 Hz each, AB system), 1.27 (6H, s, Me); ¹³C (20 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 184.9 (s), 154.4 (s), 144.9 (s), 128.3 (d), 125.5 (d), 121.5 (d), 120.8 (d), 55.8 (s), 38.6 (t), 21.0 (q); *m/z* 286 (M⁺, 100%), 285 (45), 271 (M-Me, 98), 143 (M⁺⁺, 56), 128 (24).

In methanol as the reaction medium with similar amounts of starting materials, extensive decomposition occurred and the yield of **9** fell to 80 mg (8%); 56 mg (5%) of **11** was also obtained.

Reduction of 9 : The indolocarbazole **9** (30 mg) in methanol (15 ml) was treated with NaBH₄ (250 mg). After 2 h the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, water (10 ml) added and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The tetrahydro derivative (**13**), m.p. 151°, was purified by chromatography over silica gel. The product *6a,12a*-dimethyl-*5,5a,6,6a,11,11a,12,12a*-octahydroindolocarbazole (**13**; 28 mg, 93%), m.p. 151° (benzene) was obtained in the benzene eluate on silica-gel chromatography (Found : C, 82.5; H, 7.7; N, 9.65. C₂₀H₂₂N₂ requires : C, 82.7; H, 7.6; N, 9.7%); ν_{\max} 3380, 3350, 3310, 1608, 845, 750 cm⁻¹; ν_{\max} (EtOH) 245, 300 nm (log ϵ 3.58, 3.05); δ_{H} (80 MHz, CDCl₃) 6.4–7.2 (8H, m), 3.52 (2H, dd, *J* 6.5, 5 Hz, C_{5a,11a}-H), 1.84 (2H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 1.83 (2H, d, *J* 5 Hz), 1.33 (6H, s, Me); *m/z* 290 (M⁺, 15%), 198 (8), 158 (8), 146 (27), 145 (18), 144 (100), 143 (19), 131 (36), 130 (68).

Reaction of 2-ethyl-3-methylindole (8) : 2-Ethyl-3-methylindole (954 mg, 6 mmol) in acetic acid (10 ml) and TTA (2.4 g, 6 mmol) gave *6,6a,12,12a*-tetramethyl-tetrahydroindolocarbazole (**10**; 110 mg, 11%), m.p. 270° (ethyl acetate) from the benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates : (Found : C, 83.9; H, 7.1; N, 8.9. C₂₂H₂₂N₂ requires : C, 84.0; H, 7.1; N, 8.9%); ν_{\max} 1602, 1565, 768, 750 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 225, 260 nm (log ϵ 4.78, 4.46); λ_{\max} (70% HClO₄) 242, 314 nm (log ϵ 4.56, 4.68); δ_{H} (80 MHz, CDCl₃) 7.20–7.70 (8H, m, ArH), 2.62 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz; CMe),

1.58 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz; C_{6,12} Me), 1.07 (6H, s, C_{6a,12a}-Me); *m/z* 314 (M⁺, 18%), 299 (M-Me, 100), 284 (M-2Me, 25), 269 (M-3Me, 5), 156 (24), 143 (6), 130 (13), 128 (9); ¹³C δ (20 MHz, CDCl₃) 132.3 (d), 132.0 (d), 131.4 (d), 129.5 (d), 70.7 (d), 29.0 (s), 23.9 (t), 13.5 (q), 10.4 (q). The other product was 2-acetyl-3-methylindole (**12**; 70 mg, 7%), m.p. 147°, obtained from the benzene eluates (lit.¹⁶ m.p. 149–50°) (Found : C, 76.0; H, 6.5; N, 8.0. C₁₁H₁₁NO requires : C, 76.3; H, 6.4; N, 8.1%); ν_{\max} 1626 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl); λ_{\max} (EtOH), 235, 316 nm (log ϵ 4.20, 4.32); δ_{H} (80 MHz, CDCl₃) 8.91 (1H, s, NH), 6.90–7.75 (4H, m, ArH), 2.55 (6H, s, 2Me) [2.30, 3H, s and 2.26, 3H, s in CDCl₃ + TFA]; *m/z* 173 (M⁺, 80), 158 (100), 130 (90), 103 (55), 102 (45), 77 (75).

Reduction of 10 : NaBH₄ (200 mg) was added to **10** (25 mg) in methanol (30 ml). After 24 h, the usual work-up gave *6,6a,12,12a*-tetramethyl-*5,5a,6,6a,11,11a,12,12a*-octahydroindolocarbazole (23 mg, 92%), m.p. 310° (dec.) (benzene) (Found : C, 82.8; H, 8.2; N, 8.6. C₂₂H₂₆N₂ requires : C, 83.0; H, 8.2; N, 8.8%); ν_{\max} 3388 (NH), 1610, 1253, 800, 762, 755 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 248, 295 nm (log ϵ 4.22, 3.84); δ_{H} (80 MHz, CDCl₃) 6.45–7.15 (8H, m, ArH), 3.33 (2H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, C_{5a,11a}-H), 1.80 (2H, double quartet, *J* 7, 3.5 Hz, C_{6,12}-H), 1.44 (6H, s, C_{6a,12a}-CH₃), 1.04 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C_{6,12}-CH₃).

Lead(IV) acetate oxidations : Lead(IV) acetate (1.5 g) in acetic acid (15 ml) was added slowly to a solution of the substrate (2,3-dimethylindole **7** or 2-ethyl-3-methylindole **8**) (3.5 mmol) in acetic acid (10 ml) under N₂. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4.5 h and then worked up by neutralising the acid with NaHCO₃ and extracting with CH₂Cl₂. Tlc analysis revealed the absence of the indolocarbazoles **9** or **10** respectively, in the reaction mixture. Chromatography over silica gel afforded the products **11** (150 mg, 30%) and **12** (242 mg, 40%) respectively.

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